

PEER REVIEW REPORT

Peer review report for:

Varbanova, M., Barcellos, M. D de., Kirova, M., Steur, Hans., Gellynck, X. (2025). Successful factors for industry 4.0 circularity in agri-food companies. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(4), e2024-0245. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0034-759020250409>

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Varbanova, M., Barcellos, M. D de., Kirova, M., Steur, Hans., Gellynck, X. (2025). Peer review report for: Successful factors for industry 4.0 circularity in agri-food companies. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(4), e2024-0245. *Zenodo*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17047845>

Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of the reviewers' and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited.

Reviewers:

Vilmar Antonio Gonçalves Tondolo , Universidade Federal de Pelotas, Faculdade de Administração e de Turismo, Pelotas, RS, Brazil

The second reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

The third reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 Report

Reviewer: Vilmar Antonio Gonçalves Tondolo

Date Review Returned: 16-Aug-2024

Decision: Reject & Resubmit

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Comments to the Author

I thank the authors for submitting their manuscript to the RAE/FGV/EAESP. I enjoyed reviewing the study on SUCCESSFUL FACTORS FOR INDUSTRY 4.0 CIRCULARITY IN AGRI-FOOD COMPANIES. However, I have some recommendations and suggestions. The manuscript has potential but is not ready to be published in its current form. Please see my recommendations below. I also attached the file with some recommendations. I wish you success in our study and publication.

Abstract

I believe it is more relevant to highlight the analysis approach, as it is a crucial aspect of your study and deserves more attention.

How do you analyze the impact without empirical or metanalytical data?

See additional comments on the file.

Introduction

It's not clear that the study's main contribution should be more specific and clearer (theoretically and managerial). See additional comments on the file.

Literature review

See additional comments on the file.

Methodology

See additional comments on the file.

Results

See additional comments on the file.

In general, how you present the results highlights the studies' authors. I recommend you highlight the factors. Use the elements of Tables 1 and 2 as a guide. See, as an example:

Srivastava, S.K. (2007) Green Supply-Chain Management: A State-of-the-Art Literature Review. International Journal of Management Reviews, 9, 53-80.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2370.2007.00202.x>

Agrawal, S., Singh, R.K. and Murtaza, Q. (2015) A Literature Review and Perspectives in Reverse Logistics. Resources, Conservation and Recycling, 97, 76-92.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2015.02.009>

Discussion

See additional comments on the file.

Try to remodel tables 1 and 2. See, examples in the suggested papers.

At the end of the discussion, try to propose propositions to guide further studies.

Conclusion

I recommend you reorganize the conclusion section, making clear the managerial contributions, theoretical contributions, limitations, and specific suggestions for further studies.

See additional comments on the file.

Figures

See additional comments on the file.

Finally, I recommend reading the guidelines of the MRQ journal, for which I am a reviewer. They have very important insights.

Review of Managerial Science (2023) 17:1899–1933

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-023-00668-3>

Manag Rev Q (2018) 68:103–106

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-018-0142-x>

Management Review Quarterly (2021) 71:519–524

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-021-00228-7>

Keep up your hard work.

Good luck!

Reviewer 2 Report

The second reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Reviewer 3 Report

The third reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Author's Response

dear Dr. Juliana Bonomi, Editor-in-Chief at RAE - Revista de Administração de Empresas and Dr. Simone Sehnem, Associate Editor

Thank you for inviting us to submit a revised draft of our manuscript entitled, “SUCCESSFUL FACTORS FOR INDUSTRY 4.0 CIRCULARITY IN AGRI-FOOD COMPANIES” to RAE - Revista de Administração de Empresas.

We also appreciate the time and effort you and each of the reviewers have dedicated to providing insightful feedback on ways to strengthen our paper. Thus, it is with great pleasure that we resubmit our article for further consideration. We have incorporated changes that reflect the detailed suggestions you have graciously provided. We also hope that our edits and the responses satisfactorily address all the issues and concerns you and the reviewers have noted.

To facilitate your review of our revisions, the following is a point-by-point response to the questions and comments delivered in your letter dated 24.09.2024.

Editor Suggestions:

The Associate Editor had no comments. Yet, once again, we would like to thank both reviewers for their fair assessment and valuable comments. We took their recommendations and suggestions accordingly. The publication at RAE is of high importance to our team of co-authors and your opinion is precious. If still some part of the paper doesn't respond to your expectations, please let us know and we will further work on improving the article.

Reviewer 1 - Comments:

General comments: I thank the authors for submitting their manuscript to the RAE/FGV/EAESP. I enjoyed reviewing the study on SUCCESSFUL FACTORS FOR INDUSTRY 4.0 CIRCULARITY IN AGRIFOOD COMPANIES. However, I have some recommendations and suggestions. The manuscript has potential but is not ready to be published in its current form. Please see my recommendations below. I also attached the file with some recommendations. I wish you success in our study and publication.

RESPONSE: Dear Reviewer 1, Thank you very much for your thoughtful and constructive feedback on our manuscript. We appreciate the time and effort you dedicated to reviewing our work. Your recommendations have been invaluable in helping us refine our study, and we have carefully addressed each one to enhance the manuscript's quality and clarity. Below, we detail our responses to each of your comments and describe the adjustments made. Moreover, we also added as an attachment the PDF file with specific answers to your comments. Thank you.

Comment on Abstract: I believe it is more relevant to highlight the analysis approach, as it is a crucial aspect of your study and deserves more attention. How do you analyze the impact without empirical or meta analytical data? See additional comments on the file.

RESPONSE: Thank you for your observation. We agree and the word “impact” was completely removed from the text, since interrelation hasn't been proved empirically. In the revised abstract, we have focused on the analysis and the contributions we bring, combining scoping review and content analysis.

Comment on the Introduction: It's not clear that the study's main contribution should be more specific and clearer (theoretically and managerial).

RESPONSE: Thank you for your valuable insights and constructive feedback. We have carefully reviewed and addressed each comment, and as a result, we have substantially reorganized the Introduction. Specifically, we combined the Literature Review into this section to improve coherence and provide a clear narrative.

We have emphasized the significance of digital transformation as a tool to enhance the economic competitiveness of the European Union, which aligns with the strategic focus of the European Commission. This context underscores the rationale for selecting Europe and our study's scope.

We clarified the study's contribution: to theoretically identify the critical success factors for implementing Industry 4.0 in European manufacturing SMEs. This theoretical foundation aims to serve as a basis for the subsequent development of a practical, step-by-step model tailored for management teams to effectively facilitate the transformation to Industry 4.0. Particular attention was devoted to the agri-food sector, where digitalization levels vary significantly by region, presenting additional challenges and opportunities.

We have also revised unclear sentences, added missing words, and made the text more precise. For example: “The transition towards digitalization of European manufacturing companies is considered to bring positive effects towards improved consumer experience, product quality, and innovation potential (Moeuf et al. 2018); increased profitability, reduction of defects, and rework (Yilmaz et al. 2022). By implanting the concepts of Industry 4.0, enterprises report better management performance and higher outcomes while realizing economic, social, and environmental benefits” (Sommer 2015)”.
“So far few authors have focused on the managerial perspective of Industry 4.0”. (Strange and Zucchella 2017).

Comments on Methodology: Make a figure with the published articles and respective journals. Put more emphasis on the technical part of the content analysis and not on the tools. See examples.

RESPONSE: Thank you for this very relevant suggestion. We have suggested a table with the bibliography for the scoping review and the respective journals.

We have also worked on the content analysis with NVivo elaborating more on the technical work with the NVivo software and the findings from our analysis, following the example of other academic works.

For example, we added this paragraph: Then bias was avoided through a second iteration, which involved screening all the papers manually (Felsberger et al., 2020). The results indicate that the industry manufacturing domain dominates 70% of the research field, towards 30% of papers focusing on agri-food. The focus is on sustainable I4.0 technologies for manufacturing environments, followed by technologies for supply chains, including blockchain technologies, cloud applications, or the impact of digital transformation on circular economies.

Comments on Results: Remove “interralation” if it hasn’t been proved with cluster analysis.

Comments on Discussion: Try to remodel tables 1 and 2. See, examples in the suggested papers. At the end of the discussion, try to propose propositions to guide further studies.

RESPONSE: The word “interrelation” has been replaced with “the link”. The results section now highlights the critical success factors, minimizing the emphasis on individual studies. Discussion was integrated into this section and the remodeled tables (now Tables 2 and 3) clearly summarize the factors, making the findings more accessible and actionable. Figure 5 is new and presents the framework for interconnecting authors and factors. This presentation aligns with the examples provided in your suggested references and the revised section now provides a more robust interpretation of results with practical implications.

Some suggestions for further research, for example, highlighting opportunities for empirical validation and exploration in diverse regions and emerging concepts such as Agriculture 5.0 and 6.0.

Comments Conclusion: I recommend you reorganize the conclusion section, making clear the managerial contributions, theoretical contributions, limitations, and specific suggestions for

further studies. See additional comments on the file.

RESPONSE: We agree and have reorganized the whole chapter according to the indications. Each paragraph represents a separate section from the above.

General comment: I recommend reading the guidelines of the MRQ journal, for which I am a reviewer. They have very important insights.

Review of Managerial Science (2023) 17:1899–1933

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-023-00668-3>

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Management Review Quarterly (2021) 71:519–524

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-021-00228-7>

RESPONSE: Thank you very much for the given examples, which were used as inspiration to improve the manuscript.

Authors must explicitly state the theoretical and practical implications of their findings, to emphasize transparency in research methods and analysis.

RESPONSE: We have added more clarity to our systematic review and content analysis to be better understood and reproduced. Conclusions were revised and clearly state our contributions.

Also, authors should integrate findings from various studies to provide a comprehensive overview of the topic, while in our case focusing more on factors than on authors.

RESPONSE: We did that by transforming tables, adding and revising figures and rewriting the results/discussion part.

Reviewer 2 - Comments:

General comment: The article presents an important review study to contribute to advancing knowledge. However, some points are highlighted for the article to have better organization and methodological depth.

RESPONSE: Thank you for your time and efforts in guiding us to reorganize the paper and enhance its quality.

General comment: Some parts reveal that the article was not carefully reviewed. Examples include: p. 3 line 26, the second paragraph was not completed; In Figure 3, page 27, it is as Figure 1; acronyms without their respective meaning.

RESPONSE: Thank you for this suggestion. The sentence on p. 3, line 26 has been removed and replaced with the following: “With the new Commission’s mandate and political agenda, the focus also extends to industrial sectors, aiming to boost their competitiveness on a global scale by integrating sustainable practices and advanced technologies (EC, 2022).”

The figures have been also replaced entirely with new improved ones according to your comments.

Comment on the Introduction: I suggest that the Literature Review section on page 4 (and its two subtopics) be part of the Introduction section since it describes the problem and the research gap, ending with the research questions and the objective in the last paragraph. However, connecting the paragraphs appropriately following a logical sequential line is necessary.

RESPONSE: We have incorporated your comments into combining the Literature review and the Introduction part. The latter we finalized with describing the research problems and gap, ending with the research questions and the objective and contribution. Logical sequential lines were also added, for example (p 4, line 16): “Smart organizations are also a source of competitive advantage (Cefis et al. 2023), circular economy production (Adamik et al. 2018) and green innovation (Wang 2024). To enhance the competitiveness, innovation, and growth of the European economy, it is essential that Industry 4.0 is developed uniformly across all Member States and economic sectors (Stanichkova et al., 2018). However, this presents a significant challenge for the block, as disparities exist based on company size, region, and sector (Jimeno-Morentilla et al., 2021; Kordos, 2019). This paper specifically focuses on agriculture, which is the least digitized sector but holds the highest potential for a twin transition within the EU.

Comment on the Methodology: The methodology section requires further development, making it clearer and justifying the procedures adopted:

- *Why did you use only the Web of Science?*
- *What were your search words? The article mentions words used by other authors, but it is not clear which ones were used in this article.*
- *Was the search only performed in the title of the articles? Or was it also performed in other parts, such as the abstract and keywords?*
- *Why did the work focus only on the EU?*
- *Figure 1 is in low resolution.*
- *Page 8, Line 15, mentions Figure 3 on “resulting word cloud”, but this was not presented. I recommend presenting more details on how the coding was done.*

RESPONSE:

The decision to rely exclusively on the Web of Science for this study was driven by its reputation as a high-quality, multidisciplinary research database that provides access to peer-reviewed and reputable academic literature. Moreover, the University of Gent and more precisely the Faculty of Bioscience prefers this database for the publications of its students and it is a prerequisite for the PhD defense. We acknowledge that future studies may consider integrating other databases to broaden the scope and address potential limitations.

The choice of research words was based on theories and academic works and they are the following: “Industry 4.0”, “management,” “success”, “key factors”, “digitalisation” “EU”, “Europe”; “agri-food”, “Agriculture 4.0”; “sustainable production”, “circular economy”, and “smart manufacturing”.

The article screening was conducted with specific criteria. Initially, 301 articles were found in the Web of Science database. After reviewing titles, 210 were retained, and 77 after reviewing abstracts. Some were excluded for being in non-English languages. Ultimately, 61 articles were eligible for inclusion in the systematic review, but only 48 were selected based on recency (published from 2015), journal publication (excluding conference papers), and focus on Industry 4.0 and critical success factors. This information has been added to the “Study section”.

We focused on the EU, since the EU has set concrete ambitions for the green and digital transformation of its economy. The block however lacks adequate support per sectors and regions to boost the process.

Figure 1 was replaced. The “word cloud” has been added.

CONCLUDING REMARKS: *We sincerely appreciate your thoughtful comments and queries, which have truly strengthened our manuscript. We have made every effort to incorporate your feedback and genuinely hope that the revisions resonate with you and lead to the acceptance of our submission. Thank you for your support throughout this process.*

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 Report

Reviewer: Vilmar Antonio Gonçalves Tondolo

Date Review Returned: 03-Dec-2024

Decision: Accept

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Comments to the Author

I appreciate the opportunity to review your revised work. I can see that you have made considerable efforts, and some areas have significantly improved. Thus, I recommend the publication of your manuscript. Best regards.

Reviewer 2 Report

The second reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Reviewer 3 Report

The third reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.